

SIMULATING THE PROGRESSIVE CRUSHING OF FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: Simulating the crush response of a glass fabric reinforced thin-walled laminated structural component has been undertaken using the finite element modelling method. The finite element model was developed and analyzed using the PAM-CRASH analysis tool, employing a modified bi-phase material model to describe the behaviour of the elementary ply. The material model treats the orthotropic ply as a quasi-homogeneous layer that includes progressive damage to model material fracture. Description of the material behaviour is accomplished based upon experimentally recorded stress-strain data for both tensile and compressive cases of loading. Simulation results for the demonstrator's crush response are compared to experimentally recorded data and the predicted deformation states and failure patterns show good resemblance to the experimental data. The initial load response is also well predicted by the simulation and refinement of the material characterisation process is proposed to improve the models accuracy over the full range of crushing.

KEYWORDS: progressive damage, material characterisation, finite element modelling

INTRODUCTION

Finite element modelling of a glass fabric reinforced laminated demonstrator component has been undertaken employing multi-layered shell elements for discretisation of the demonstrator's structure. Description of the elementary fabric ply behaviour is accomplished using a modified bi-phase material model [1, 2] which treats the composite ply as a quasi-homogeneous orthotropic layer that includes progressive damage. Characterisation of the material ply is completed through uniaxial tensile and compressive testing of material specimens. The non-linear explicit finite element dynamic analysis code, PAM-CRASH, is used for simulation of the demonstrator's response to a crushing load with a constant velocity of 150mm/s. The simulated load-displacement response is compared to the experimentally recorded curve and a comparison of the predicted deformation modes is also made with deformation states recorded during experiment.

Modelling the crush response of composite components requires prediction of the material's response right up to the point of ultimate failure. To this end, composite materials under load generally experience internal material failure before any change in the material macroscopic appearance (and response) is observed. Different modes of internal failure have been identified and accepted for fibre composite materials (e.g. [3]) with the prevalence of any failure mode under a given loading being dependant upon the direction and nature of loading at the infinitesimal material level. The four accepted modes of failure are: (i) matrix microcracking, (ii) fibre/matrix debonding, (iii) fibre breaking and (iv) delamination.

The progressive nature of composite failure leads to the progressive damage modelling for composite materials in order to predict the material and structural response over large displacements. Progressive damage modelling of fibre composite materials is integrated into mathematical models using continuum damage mechanics (CDM) as a basis and various approaches have been developed (and implemented) in order to capture the effect of the progressive internal material failures on the overall material macroscopic response. In order to model the behaviour of a laminate (made up of a number of plies) damage law must be applied at the material ply level since stresses vary from one ply to the next. The ply may then either be considered as a whole [4] or the fibre and matrix behaviours can be considered separately and then combined to describe the ply behaviour [1].

The bi-phase model treats fibre and matrix phases separately, using the measured elastic properties of a unidirectional ply, together with the known fibre properties and fibre volume fraction, to deduce the elastic properties of the matrix phase [5]. Damage law is implemented according to:

$$E = E_0(1 - d) \quad (1)$$

where E_0 is the initial modulus, E the instantaneous modulus and d the damage parameter lying in the range $0 \leq d \leq 1$. Damage parameter is defined separately for the separate material phases and at any given time is the sum of volumetric damage, due to a volumetric equivalent strain, and shear damage, due to a shear equivalent strain. The model also allows for separate definition of tensile and compressive behaviour in the principal material directions.

A significant amount of research effort has been dedicated to studying the energy absorption for the axial crushing of composite structures, typically with tubular cross section, e.g. [6 – 7]. The work of Mamalis et al. [8] provides a comprehensive overview of the axial crushing and bending collapse of composite tubes of varied cross-sectional shape. The attention to this area of research is driven by the ability of the composites to absorb a greater amount of energy per unit mass under controlled progressive axial crushing, an advantage for application as crash energy absorbers. The collapse of a thin-walled structural component under crushing type loads, on the other hand, occurs due to a combination of bending and tearing of the structural shell as crushing progresses and may include cases of local and global buckling. For the general crushing of a mixed structure, a complex combination of axial and bending collapse will occur depending upon the nature of the loading and the orientation of the various sub-structures to the crushing loads. The present work aims to predict the composite structural component's response to crushing type loads, dominated by the combined bending and membrane modes of response of the thin-walled structure.

PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODELLING

The bi-phase model is a heterogeneous material model adapted to unidirectional continuous fibre reinforced composites or composite fabrics. The material stiffness is calculated by superimposing the effects of an orthotropic material phase (matrix) and a one dimensional material phase (fibres). Each phase (fibre, matrix) has its own rheological law, e.g., an elastic/brittle orthotropic or micro-fracturing brittle damage law for the matrix phase and a unidirectional elastic-brittle damage law for the fibres.

For this model the orthotropic character of the cloth and of the unidirectional composite layers of a stackup can be modelled in two principal ways: either using two material phases, namely fibres plus matrix ('classical' model), or using one material phase, namely an orthotropic layer only ('modified' model) [5]. Using the 'modified' approach, the material is modelled as a single orthotropic layer and separate fibre and matrix properties need not be specified. In this case the measured composite properties are used to describe the quasi-homogeneous layer.

Damage law for the bi-phase model is implemented by a reduction in stiffness, as given by:

$$\mathbf{C}(d) = \mathbf{C}_0 \times (1 - d) \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{C} is the instantaneous stiffness matrix, \mathbf{C}_0 is the initial undamaged stiffness matrix and d is a unitless scalar damage parameter that is a function of strain. As for the material elastic constants, damage function for the bi-phase model is defined separately for cases of tension and compression, and may propagate independently for matrix and fibres when both material phases are employed.

Damage function is separated into volumetric and shear components as given by

$$d(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = d_v(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_v) + d_s(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s) \quad (3)$$

where d_v is the volumetric damage as a function of volumetric strain

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_v = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{11} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{22} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{33} \quad (4)$$

and d_s is a shear induced damage as a function of equivalent shear strain

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \left[(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{11}^2 + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{22}^2 + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{33}^2 - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{11}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{22} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{22}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{33} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{11}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{33}) + 3\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{12}^2 + 3\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{23}^2 + 3\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{13}^2 \right]} \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) are the components of the strain tensor.

Description of the damage functions, $d_v(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_v)$ and $d_s(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s)$, is accomplished by choosing three critical damage points from the relevant stress-strain diagram (Fig. 1). They are the initial damage point (i), the intermediate damage point (I) and the ultimate damage point (u). The damage function is then assumed to be piecewise linear between the critical damage points and is subject to the limits $0 \leq d \leq 1$. Evolution of damage begins when the initial damage point is passed (measured in terms of strain), since $d = 0$ for $0 \leq \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \leq \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i$. The damage value then increases linearly over the range $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \leq \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \leq \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1$, where damage equals d_1 when strain equals $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1$. Damage continues linearly over the range $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 \leq \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \leq \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_u$, until the ultimate damage point is reached ($d = d_u$ when $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_u$). For $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} > \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_u$, the damage value grows asymptotically from d_u to a value of 1.

Description of the fabric reinforced orthotropic material requires nine independent elastic constants. These are the elastic moduli in the principal material directions (E_1, E_2, E_3), the shear moduli (G_{12}, G_{13}, G_{23}) and Poisson's ratios ($\nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23}$). In addition, the full set of material characterisation parameters required for progressive damage description should include critical strains ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_u$) and damage values (d_1, d_u).

Fig. 1 Damage description for the bi-phase model

Implementation of the finite element model used to simulate the laminated demonstrator's response to a constant velocity crushing load firstly requires characterisation of the individual plies that are used in the construction of the component. In order to characterise the material, specimens have been manufactured using the same material constituents (fabric, resin) and fabrication process as for the demonstrator. The specimens have been tested under uniaxial tension and compression and the material characterisation parameters necessary for describing the behaviour of the elementary fabric reinforced ply were calculated from the experimentally recorded stress-strain data. The critical damage points (*i*, *l*, *u*) have been extracted from experimental tensile and compressive stress-strain curves (Fig. 2) and the resulting material characterisation parameters are shown in Table 1. Critical strains have been calculated using tensile and compressive test data and Eqns (4), (5), modified for uniaxial loading, as follows:

$$\varepsilon_v = (1 - \nu_{12} - \nu_{13}) \varepsilon_{11} \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_s = \frac{\varepsilon_{11}}{\sqrt{3}} (1 + \nu_{12} + \nu_{13} - \nu_{12}\nu_{13} + \nu_{12}^2 + \nu_{13}^2)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

Calibration of the material model was subsequently completed through simulation of the uniaxial tests and satisfactory results were obtained (see Fig. 2).

(a) tension

(b) compression

Fig. 2 Material characterisation and calibration

Table 1 Material characterisation parameters

	MATERIAL CONSTANTS						DAMAGE PARAMETERS			
	Tensile moduli (GPa)		Shear moduli (GPa)		Poisson's ratios		Critical strains		Damage values	
TENSILE	E_1	17	G_{12}^{**}	5.5	ν_{21}	0.17	ϵ_{vi}	0.0053	-	-
	E_2	17	G_{23}^*	3.4	ν_{32}	0.30	ϵ_{v1}	0.0100	d_1	0.12
	E_3^*	13	G_{13}^*	3.4	ν_{31}	0.30	ϵ_{vu}	0.0106	d_u	0.95
COMPRESSIVE	E_1	4.37	G_{12}^{**}	5.5	ν_{21}	0.17	ϵ_{si}	0.0451	-	-
	E_2	4.37	G_{23}^*	3.4	ν_{32}	0.30	ϵ_{s1}	0.0537	d_1	0.07
	E_3	3	G_{13}^*	3.4	ν_{31}	0.30	ϵ_{su}	0.0902	d_u	0.74

* [9], ** [10]

LAMINATED DEMONSTRATOR

The geometry of the demonstrator has been selected to be complex enough that successful simulation of the demonstrator's response would provide a significant level of confidence in the modelling methodology. The shape of the demonstrator component is selected to be representative of an automotive compartment such as the compartment typically used to house a spare wheel (Fig. 3). This provides a sufficiently complex geometry consisting of flat sections (which make up the component's rectangular base plate and circular cylinder end) and a curved cylindrical sidewall. Component dimensions are shown in Fig. 4. The laminated demonstrator is constructed using 8 layers of 290g/m² twill weave glass fabric (suppliers *AMT*, South Africa) in an Ampreg20 epoxy resin system (suppliers *SP systems International*).

Fig. 3 Laminated demonstrator geometry

Fig. 4 Demonstrator dimensions

Definition of fibre orientation angles over separate parts of the demonstrator is accomplished using two separate coordinate systems. Fibre orientation on the flat parts of the component (rectangular base plate and cylinder end) is defined by angle ϕ_1 , in terms of the xy Cartesian coordinate system (Fig 5(a)), and fibre orientation on the cylinder sidewall is defined by angle ϕ_2 (Fig. 5(b)), in terms of the cylindrical coordinate system shown.

With each fabric layer represented according to its warp direction, the following stacking sequences were obtained during demonstrator manufacture (orientation code as per ASTM D6507).

FLATS (ϕ_1)

$[0]_8$

SIDEWALL (ϕ_2)

$[0\ 45]_{2S}$

The real laminated demonstrator's construction is shown together with the construction used in the modelling environment in Fig. 6. The modelled sidewall construction is the same as the real demonstrator's construction, consisting of eight layers alternately stacked at 0° and 45° . Orientations on the flats are simplified from eight layers to an equivalent four layer system, with four 0.6mm layers used to represent the eight 0.3mm layers that make up the real component. The demonstrator components were manufactured using a hot vacuum bagging process together with hand layup of resin and fabric patterns. Curing was completed through heating to 90°C for a period of 35min at a vacuum pressure of 0.8 bar.

Fig. 5 Separate definition of fibre orientation for flats and sidewall

Fig. 6 Comparison of real demonstrator construction with the modelled material layup

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A four noded quadrilateral shell element has been employed for modelling of the demonstrator geometry. Application of the bi-phase model for shell elements in the PAM-CRASH code corresponds to Material Type 130 [11] which is a multi-layered material tailored for the description of orthotropic laminates. The demonstrator geometry was developed using the Rhinoceros 3D software and then imported into MSC.NASTRAN for generation of the finite element mesh (see Fig. 7). The demonstrator geometry was thus modelled (and meshed) using the midplane of the demonstrator component. The meshed model has been imported into PAM-CRASH.

To aid the generation of a structured mesh, a quarter of the geometry is initially meshed and then reflected twice in order to generate a mesh representing the full component. Establishment of a well graded and mapped mesh is also accomplished by segmenting the geometry and setting mesh sizes along the boundary curves. To enable description of separate laminate layups for the demonstrator flats and sidewalls, the flat sections and sidewall are meshed with separate plate property ID's in the NASTRAN environment, creating two separate material regions.

In the Generis environment (PAM-CRASH) two separate groups of nodes have been defined (Fig. 8). The nodes are separated into two groups, one for each clamped edge, and the constrained nodes represent the parts of the component that are clamped during physical testing. The fixed end has all nodal degrees of freedom fixed and the row of nodes at the inside edge of the fixed end are defined as a section for reporting the reaction force. In order to further represent experiment, the velocity in the x -direction (see Fig. 8) of the moving edge is set to equal to the velocity of loading for the experimental case concerned.

Fig. 7 Generating the prototype mesh

Fig. 8 Simulation boundary conditions

DEMONSTRATOR TESTING AND SIMULATION

Testing of the laminated demonstrator was completed using an MTS servo hydraulic dynamic testing rig. The edges of the component were clamped (as employed for description of the problem boundary conditions) and the moving end was forced to translate at the prescribed velocity (150mm/s). Numerical data obtained from the test are the applied load and displacement over time, allowing for plotting of the experimental force-displacement history. The finite element model, developed as described (see Model Development section), has been employed to simulate the laminated demonstrator's response to a crushing load with constant velocity of 150mm/s and clamped boundaries, as implemented during testing. The PAM-CRASH analysis tool has been used for this purpose and description of the elementary ply using the bi-phase material model is undertaken using the calibrated material characterisation shown in Fig. 2.

The comparison of the simulated results with the experimental data is made by plotting the simulated force-displacement history together with the force-displacement history recorded during experiment (Fig. 9). Also shown is a comparison of the experimentally recorded deformation states (recorded using a digital camera) and deformation states obtained from the simulation (Fig. 9). The simulated and experimentally recorded data for the crushing of the laminated demonstrator shows good agreement between the predicted and experimentally recorded deformation plots. Further, the predicted peak load (6.5kN) and displacement at peak (3.9mm) are found to agree with the experimentally recorded peak (4.5mm, 7.7kN) within an accuracy of 16% (Fig. 9).

A comparison of the real, schematic and simulated failure patterns is provided in Fig. 10. The real failure pattern (Fig. 10(a)) is a photographic record of the component after testing and shows the location of the major cracks and fold lines that develop during the crushing process. The schematic failure pattern (Fig. 10(b)) is a representation of the real failure pattern, where the three major cracks (numbered 1 to 3) that have been observed during the crushing experiment are indicated. The areas of damage reported from the simulation that correspond to the major failures observed from testing are numbered accordingly (Fig. 10(c)). The comparison of the real, schematic and simulated failure patterns shows the areas of damage reported from simulation that correspond to failure in the real component.

Fig. 9 Comparison of simulated and experimental response for demonstrator, $v = 150 \text{ mm/s}$

Fig. 10 Comparison of LPT1 failure patterns (real, schematic and simulated)

CONCLUSIONS

Modelling the crush response of a laminated demonstrator component with complex geometry has been undertaken using the bi-phase material model included with the PAM-CRASH analysis tool. The modelling procedure used to simulate the response of the thin-walled laminated component has involved material characterisation and calibration, finite element mesh development, implementation of appropriate problem boundary conditions and complete description of the material layup over the volume of the component. Composite material layup modelling included the selection of separate material regions and careful choice of the finite elements' spatial orientation. The meshing process employed has also demonstrated how the control of mesh grading along boundary curves of individual surface segments could be used to manipulate the final structure of the finite element mesh.

Development of the modelling methodology has been completed to a level that results in simulated deformation states showing good resemblance to the real deformation states recorded during the crushing experiment. Critical regions of failure have been predicted effectively as indicated by the onset and further development of damage in those elements of the discretised structure where failure occurs in the real component. The component's initial response has been accurately reproduced during simulation and refinement of the material characterisation process could be used to improve the accuracy over the full range of displacement experienced during the progressive crushing process.

The investigation outlines a method by which the bi-phase material model may be used, together with the PAM-CRASH code, to obtain solutions for the virtual prototyping and design of thin-walled laminated composite structures that are subjected to crushing loads.

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